

Supplementary Material

Supplementary Table 1. Overall sample information and patients' characteristics.

	Type	gender	age	Mayo endoscopy score	Mayo score	Medication	distribution of disease¹	disease duration
1	UC	F	53	3	12	5-ASA, steroids	E3	1 year
2	UC	M	29	3	7	5-ASA, steroids	E2	5 mouths
3	UC	M	40	3	11	5-ASA, steroids	E2	4 mouths
4	UC	M	54	2	6	5-ASA	E2	3 years
5	UC	F	52	1	6	no treatment	E2	1 year
6	UC	F	53	1	5	no treatment	E1	1 year
7	UC	F	42	2	8	5-ASA, Azathioprine	E2	8 mouths
8	UC	M	53	2	8	5-ASA	E3	2 years
9	UC	F	65	2	7	5-ASA	E2	15 years
10	UC	F	54	3	10	no treatment	E2	1.5 years
11	UC	F	28	3	12	5-ASA	E2	2 years
12	UC	M	20	1	6	5-ASA, steroids	E1	1 year
13	UC	M	32	3	8	5-ASA	E2	7 mouths
14	UC	M	59	2	6	5-ASA	E1	1 year
15	UC	F	47	2	8	5-ASA, steroids	E2	1 year
16	UC	M	49	3	8	5-ASA	E3	2 years
17	UC	M	31	2	11	no treatment	E2	1 mouth
18	UC	F	53	3	12	5-ASA, steroids	E3	1 year
19	UC	F	56	2	6	5-ASA, steroids	E3	5 years
20	UC	M	27	2	6	no treatment	E3	2 years
21	UC	F	46	1	4	5-ASA	E1	8 years
22	UC	F	65	1	5	5-ASA, steroids, Sulfasalazine	E2	2 weeks
23	UC	M	29	3	12	5-ASA, steroids, Azathioprine	E3	1 year
24	UC	F	49	2	12	5-ASA, steroids	E3	6 years
25	UC	M	48	2	7	5-ASA	E3	8 mouths
26	UC	F	51	2	6	5-ASA, steroids, Azathioprine	E2	1 year
27	UC	F	27	2	6	Sulfasalazine	E2	5 mouths
28	UC	F	53	1	5	no treatment	E1	2 years
29	UC	M	49	2	8	5-ASA	E2	2 weeks
30	UC	M	49	2	7	5-ASA	E2	3 years
31	HC	M	53					

32	HC	F	60
33	HC	M	27
34	HC	F	56
35	HC	M	33
36	HC	F	63
37	HC	F	51
38	HC	M	41
39	HC	F	32
40	HC	F	56
41	HC	M	53
42	HC	M	32
43	HC	M	42
44	HC	F	45
45	HC	F	46
46	HC	F	50
47	HC	F	44
48	HC	F	46
49	HC	F	53
50	HC	M	56
51	HC	F	46
52	HC	F	46
53	HC	M	52
54	HC	M	44
55	HC	F	52

E1, Rectum; E2, Sigmoid and left colon; E3, Entire colon. UC, UC patients; HC, Healthy control; F, female; M, male.

Supplementary Table 2. Primer sequences for qRT-PCR

Gene	Primer sequence
GADPH	F:5' GTCTCCTCTGACTTCAACAGCG 3' R :5' ACCACCCTGTTGCTGTAGCCAA 3'
ZO-1	F:5' AATCCCTATCACCCAGCGTC 3' R:5' CCTTCTGCCCCACTTCAGTC 3'
occludin	F:5' TGCGGCGAGCGGATTG 3' R:5' TCAGGCCTGTAAGGAGGTGG 3'
CLDN-2	F:5' CATCCCAGAGAAATCGCTCCAACACTAC 3' R:5' AGGCTGTAGGAATTGAACTCACTCTTG 3'
Hsa_circ_0001021	F:5' TTGGCAGAGCAGTTTGTTCCTC 3' R:5' CTCACCGTCAGGGATGGGTCTAC 3'
miR-224-5p	HmiRQP0343
smad4	F:5' CCAGCTCTGTTAGCCCCATC 3' R:5' TACTGGCAGGCTGACTTGTG 3'
hsa_circ_0001021 probe	5' AATAATTAATTTACACCTGAACTGAAGTGGCTGA 3'

Si-hsa_circ_0001021
miR-224-5p mimics
miR-224-5p inhibitor

5' CCACTTCAGTTCAGGTGTA 3'
F:5' UCAAGUACUAGUGGUUCCGUUUAG 3'
R:5' AAACGGAACCACUAGUGAUUGAUU 3'
5' CUAACGGAACCACUAGUGACUUGA 3'

Supplementary Figure 1 Correlation analysis of test samples.

(A) CircRNAs data correlation analysis of test samples. (B) MiRNAs data correlation analysis of test samples. (C) MRNAs data correlation analysis of test samples.